

Becoming a Student in Europe

A Comparative Social Portrait of Higher Education Students in the Major Regions of the European Higher Education Area

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The essay presents several key outcomes of the fifth wave of the pan-European survey EURO-STUDENT, which was implemented in 29 European higher education area (EHEA) countries from 2012–2014. The article starts with a brief description of the survey, followed by a chapter revealing certain background trends in the historical and social dynamics of higher education participation in Europe. The next part outlines several key features of student populations in Europe, such as their familial background, the socio-economic, educational and migration identities of students' parents, and describes the timing of the transition to higher education and other socio-demographic features of student strata that include age and students with children. All the analyses were done using the geographical framework that subdivides the whole population of the survey into four major clusters: Northern, Western and Southern ones as well as a cluster of NIS countries. The concluding section discusses possible practical implications of the empirically observed trends and values describing the EHEA student population, namely, the steady transition to the mass model of higher education that follows the original concept of Martin Trow, the diversification of the student population in the social structure in Europe and the considerable regional variation in the student body in different parts of the European Higher Education Area.

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**Based on the 5th wave
of the EUROSTUDENT
survey (E:V)**

1. Preface

This essay is based on the data from the 5th wave of the EUROSTUDENT survey, which will be referred to in this document as ‘E:V’ and took place between 2012 and 2014 with more than 200,000 participating respondents.

Many readers may be acquainted with the series of two compendiums published every third year during the last decades, in advance to the regular meetings of EHEA’s Ministers responsible for higher education. The recent issues of these papers, offering a large overview, from 2015 are *Social and Economic Conditions of Student Life in Europe: Synopsis of Indicators E:V 2012–2015* (Hauschildt, 2015) and *The European Higher Education Area: Bologna Process Implementation Report* (EC, 2015).

The former book presents and comments data yielded in the course of the fifth wave of the pan-European survey EUROSTUDENT, while the latter book uses background data gathered in the course of the survey to report on the implementation of Bologna-process goals. Very compact bits of survey results, presented by thematic “Intelligence Briefs” (<http://www.eurostudent.eu/results/reports>), as well as several national reports and analyses can also be found on the project’s website.

This line-up of project-related publications does not extend to journal-formatted articles that present and discuss survey outcomes in a way that combines illustrative data-show and related contextual descriptive analysis. This essay is intended to attempt such an article, thus filling an information gap.

This article starts with a brief description of the survey and short review of the historical and social dynamics of higher education (HE) participation in Europe and describes the student population of EHEA. The essay is titled “Becoming a Student in Europe” and includes data on familial roots of HE students, their qualification routes and transition to HE. The concluding section discusses possible practical implications that could be drawn from the presented and discussed survey data.

2. Introduction

2.1 The EUROSTUDENT Survey: Key Features

EUROSTUDENT survey is one of the most comprehensive empirical tools designed to measure present-day studentship in Europe, thus contributing both to the formulation and implementation of evidence-based policies of HE in the EHEA countries and to the advancement of scholarships by means of higher education as an important societal sphere. For an overview of other student surveys in Europe, see, for instance, Klemenčič and Chirikov (2015).

The coordinators of the EUROSTUDENT network describe the objectives, methodologies, addressees and the core content of the cross-country survey of students in EHEA as follows:

The main aim of the EUROSTUDENT project is to collate comparable data on the social dimension of European higher education. It focuses on the socio-economic background and on the living conditions of students, but it also investigates temporary international mobility. The project strives to provide reliable and insightful cross-country comparisons. It does this through coupling a central coordination approach with a strong network of national partners in each participating country. In this way, an assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of the respective national frameworks in international comparison can be made.

The main users of our findings are higher education policy makers at national and European level, researchers in this field, managers of higher education institutions and, of course, students all over Europe.

The reporting structure of EUROSTUDENT consists of a comparative report and a more detailed, searchable database that enables users to download data and a full National Profile for each country. The national and comparative data have also been used for many associated reports. (www.eurostudent.eu/about/intentions)

The fifth wave of the EUROSTUDENT survey was implemented in 2012–2014 in 29 EHEA countries among more than 200,000 respondents. Individual sample size varies by country from 41,656 respondents in Austria to 1,190 in Malta with a mean average around 7,000 respondents per country. However, the median country-sample size was 3,510 students.

Key features of the survey

The core-questionnaire of the EUROSTUDENT survey included 58 standardised questions, combined into more than 100 derivative indicators. Each country was free to add specific questions and modules to their national questionnaires.

The resulting database comprises the following major themes, data for which have been calculated from the answers to individual questions. These themes are:

- a demographics and social background of national student populations, major characteristics of national student populations;
- b transition into higher education, access and qualification routes;
- c accommodation and housing situation;
- d students' resources and expenses;
- e student's employment;
- f time-planning of students;
- g mobility and internationalisation;
- h students' assessment of their studies; and
- i future plans of students, including employability and continued studies.

As regards the geographical scope of E:V, one should bear in mind that the fifth wave was implemented only in 29 out of 48 EHEA countries. The full list of participating countries is shown in the next text box of the following section. It is a real pity that countries such as the UK, Spain, Portugal, Turkey and Greece have not taken part this time. Nevertheless, one should consider the yielded geographical coverage as fairly representative for the whole supra-region of EHEA.

2.2 Methodology (Grouping) Used in This Article

This article analyses the survey outcomes from 29 EHEA countries. With an exception of the four NIS countries, all other survey participants are either members of the European Union or accession countries.

Geographical clusters

There are multiple ways for clustering countries for comparative reasons, including groupings along political such as groups of post-socialist or old-EU countries, and economic, for example the GDP per capita, criteria. In this article, the geographical approach is deployed since it turned out to be quite an informative one; it allows grasping the wider variation of European contexts, without overburdening the social analysis with unnecessary economic or political connotations. The four geographical clusters used in the analysis include 'North' (Scandinavia, Baltics – in total eight countries), 'West' (Western Europe – eight countries), 'South' (Mediterranean and Black Sea regions – nine countries) and the 'Eurostudent-NIS' cluster (four countries).

In addition, a benchmark 'E:V average', was calculated for all 29 E:V countries, it is applied as a universal measurement of the whole popula-

tion of the survey. Such clustering provides sufficient analytical power and allows for compact and informative charts for just five objects.

For the purpose of the given article, the following grouping of EUROSTUDENT survey's (E:V) countries is used:

- **Cluster North** includes the following EHEA countries: Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway and Sweden.
- **Cluster West** is composed of Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, the Netherlands, Poland, Slovakia and Switzerland.
- **Cluster South** consists of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, France, Italy, Montenegro, Malta, Romania, Serbia and Slovenia.
- **Cluster NIS** counts Armenia, Georgia, Russia and Ukraine.

If a generic cycle of student life can be described as consisting of three major stages, where the first part would be the transition into the system of higher education of 'becoming a student', the second stage is the immediate higher education experience of 'being a student' and the third phase embraces the post-university life called 'life after graduation', then the major empirical contents of the given article that deals with the E:V survey data is dedicated to the initial stage of the process of obtaining the higher education.

**Phases of student life
and the major subject of
the article**

3. Background of Theoretic and Statistic Findings

3.1 On the Concept of the Social Dimension of Higher Education (SDHE)

Higher or tertiary education is increasingly turning into mass education or even a universal phenomenon in all modern industrial and post-industrial countries, with all the advantages and disadvantages of this crucial change. The term 'mass education' stands for the opposite to 'elitist' mode of educational involvement, and 'universal education' is a label for a system that accommodates 50% and more of the total eligible population. These conceptual terms were introduced into the HE analytical discourses in the early 1970s by Martin Trow (Trow, 1973).

Trow's famous conceptual framework suggests the following benchmarks to mark up the dynamics of the process of the gradual expansion of higher education: the 'elitist' mode of HE, with a gross enrolment ratio (GER) up to 15%, 'mass education' with a GER between 15% and 50%, and the 'universal' higher education (GER above 50%).

**Key concept of the
dynamics of the modern
higher education**

Intense social, political and academic debates are taking place about whether HE must now be considered a basic and granted human right, or whether it should remain just a socially supported ‘window of opportunity’ for all people who aspire to it and a mere ‘service’ rendered to the citizens under the auspices of the state. This can, for instance, be seen in an article discussing the issue of HE as a universal human right (McCowan, 2012), a student appeal from 2003 against the ‘commodification’ of higher education by Stefan Bienefeld (2003), and an anthology dedicated to the discussion of the recent wave of the privatisation of higher education and raising tuition fees in England (Holmwood, 2011).

As a matter of practical midline, a concept of the ‘social dimension of higher education’ (SDHE), along with its sister-principle of ‘lifelong learning’ (LLL), were introduced and adopted in the past decade as an important aspect of the Bologna Process and declared as one of the governing rules for the EHEA.

The SDHE principle

The SDHE principle was most clearly defined in the London Communiqué of 2007 of the conference of EHEA Ministers responsible for higher education:

We share the societal aspiration that the student body entering, participating in and completing higher education at all levels should reflect the diversity of our populations. We reaffirm the importance of students being able to complete their studies without obstacles related to their social and economic background. We therefore continue our efforts to provide adequate student services, create more flexible learning pathways into and within higher education, and to widen participation at all levels on the basis of equal opportunity. (EHEA Ministerial Conference, 2007)

SDHE is understood, on the one hand, as a matter of achieving the targeted social coherence, accessibility of HE and inclusion in Europe by means of securing greater equity and justice in access to HE for the underrepresented social groups. This is declared to be a specific target for HE governance, like a social aspect of any policy, in this case concerning national and international policies with regard to higher education. This is a very pragmatic and utilitarian *political* approach to the issue.

SDHE at a glance

The main features of SDHE are:

- achievement of social coherence in a society through the recruitment of HE students from the previously underrepresented social groups and strata;
- sufficient support to students securing their well-being and the successful completion of their studies; and
- sets of measures enabling the life-long learning.

On the other hand, SDHE is simultaneously interpreted as a matter of securing the well-being and provision of sufficient support to HE students, thus allowing them to pursue their studies and accomplish their HE programme smoothly and without any major social or economic obstacles, caused by students' social and economic standing. This stands for practical sets of distinct economic, social and pedagogical measures.

The first aspect means looking at society at large from the HE perspective, i.e. from a distinct social institution on the whole mechanism of the social body, of which this institution is an integral part, and answers the question, 'What can HE do for society at large?' One relevant answer would be, 'Participation in HE can and should better reflect the diversity of the population'. The second aspect is opposite in nature; it answers the question, 'What can society at large do for HE and for HE students?' This is the view from society at large into the issues of one of its functional institutions; the suitable answer would be, 'We can provide better services to (willing) students and thus assure that they are able to complete their studies smoothly.'

Two different approaches to SDHE

Since the late 1990s, the Bologna process has been accompanying the trend towards massification and universalization of HE by providing it with the necessary elements of systemic unification and harmonisation of educational standards, alongside the newly-introduced declaration of the necessity for measures that target the SDHE and the promotion of the LLL principle.

Both aspects of the term 'social dimension' outlined above would need to be based on an accurate and profound empirical fundament for the formulation of the related policies, especially if they involve the development of evidence-based measures.

3.2 Historic and Social Dynamics of Higher Education Participation and Attainment in EUROSTUDENT's Sample of EHEA Countries

As it is well-known, the trend towards the increasing massification and universalization of higher education is observed throughout the whole of Europe, and no less, as should be added, in the USA, Australia and Japan. The majority of secondary school alumni in EHEA countries are now opting for tertiary education; The average GER for 29 E:V countries in the sample scores at 66% averaged over the period between 2010 and 2014. (see Figure 1). This means that nowadays up to two thirds of secondary schools alumni are entering the tertiary education institutions, either immediately after high school graduation, or with a delay. These average values vary heavily per region and individual countries. For example, the GER figures for 2014 ranged from 33% in Georgia to 94% in Finland in the E:V sample.

Key figures on GER and attainment

Key figures on higher education enrolment and the cumulative attainment in EHEA are:

- The average GER in the E:V sample has reached 66% in the 2010s (growth 3.2 times during the last half a century) with the highest GER is measured in the Northern cluster (76%); and
- the cumulative HE attainment of population has reached 27% by 2010s as an E:V average with the highest rate achieved in post-soviet countries (NIS cluster), fixed at 43%.

Growth of gross enrolment ratio (GER)

The dynamics of HE enrolment is also very visible in the EHEA region during the last 50 years, or in the course of life of just two generations. In E:V countries, the gross enrolment ratio has grown 3.2 times during 1970–2014, from the modest minority of 20% of the respective age cohort to the convincing majority of 66%. The most impressive growth can be observed in the Western E:V region, where GER has increased 4.3 times, from 15% to 65%, followed by the Southern cluster (growth 3.9 times, from 15% to 60%) and the group of Northern E:V countries (increase 3.2 times, from 24% to 76%). The related growth rate in NIS countries of the survey remained quite modest (1.4 times), although it starts with the highest position in the region and grew up from 42% to 60%.

Figure 1 Participation in HE (GER, tertiary education) averages per decade, major geographical clusters and NIS countries, in % of the respective age cohort¹

¹ UIS, UNESCO Institute for Statistics; Number of students enrolled in a given level of education, regardless of age, is expressed as a percentage of the official school-age population corresponding to the same level of education. For tertiary level, the population used is the 5-year age group starting from the official secondary school graduation age.

The HE attainment rate of the adult population grew accordingly, reaching by mid-2010s the average value of 27% for the whole group of E:V countries in the sample, with a minimum value of 11% in Bosnia and Herzegovina and the maximum rate of HE penetration of 60% in Russia. The following figure illustrates the achieved status quo in HE attainment in the EHEA sub-regions. The attainment rate ranges from the lowest score in the E:V Southern cluster (every fifth adult, or 18%) up to the highest value for the group of NIS countries (43%).²

Growth of HE attainment rate

Figure 2 Higher Education attainment of adult population³ (UNESCO-UIS) in 2011–2014, in %⁴

The snapshot of the current situation with the relationship between the two key indicators describing the overall quantitative performances of national systems of higher education is shown on the scatter chart (Figure 3). The overall dynamics of the process moves the objects on the scatter to the right-hand upper corner with gross enrolment ratio (horizontal axis) growing naturally faster than the attainment (vertical axis).

² Starting from 1976, the International Classification of Higher Education (ISCED) defines higher or tertiary education starting from the level 5 (first university degree or equivalent). Nowadays, according to ISCED-2011, HE embraces educational levels 5 to 8, where the fifth level stands for 'short first tertiary programmes' and the eighth level designates an attainment at the level of Ph.D.

³ UNESCO Institute for Statistics (<http://data.uis.unesco.org>). Individual country data refer to the years 2011 to 2014, the latest year available is taken for the analysis. No reliable data for ISCED 6-8 for Russia.

⁴ The large difference in NIS cluster between the attainment rates at ISCED grades 5 and 6–8 is due to the later adoption of the Bologna grading of the levels of study as well as due to the UNESCO conventional statistical accounting of the previous 5-years long standard soviet HE leading to the degree of Specialist at the level of ISCED-5 (ISCED of 2011), which is in formal terms below the newly introduced Bachelor degree that is counted at ISCED-6 level. Therefore, the correct assessment of the cumulative HE attainment in Russia and some other countries is only possible as a sum of all ISCED levels 5-8.

Figure 3 Relationships between the HE enrolment and HE attainment rates in 2010 and the dynamics of E:V average values over the last decade (UIS)

Higher education as a right and not a privilege

Most of the ongoing debates on the practical implication of HE becoming mass education refer to the works of Martin Trow, who was discussing the transition of American HE system from an elitist to a mass institution and its further critical expansion toward the universal system of HE in the US in the 1970s (Trow, 2010). As Voldemar Tomusk, the modern European critical philosopher and sociologist of education summarises,

... Trow looked at US higher education as it had been expanding from a highly elitist system where only some 5 percent of the age cohort group had access to it to a universal system, where 50 percent or more had access to post-secondary education, identifying a qualitative shift at the point of 15 percent access. At that point higher education is no longer seen as a privilege, but as a right; turning into an obligation at the next juncture of 50 percent access. (Tomusk, 2016, pp. 143–144)

Thus, in these terms, the coverage of higher education in EHEA's subsample of E:V countries has clearly exceeded the Trow's conventional benchmark of 50 percent in HE enrolment. Using his conceptual language, one can say that HE participation has reached the degree, when it is often perceived as a social norm, or an assumed 'moral obligation'

of younger and older alumni of secondary education from the upper and middle classes (Brennan, 2004).

The ease of access to higher education is closely linked to conceptions that people – students and their parents, and increasingly college and university teachers and administrators – have of college and university attendance. When access is highly limited, it is generally seen as a privilege, either of birth or talent, or both. When more than about 15% of the relevant age group have access, people increasingly begin to see entry to higher education as a right for those who have certain formal qualifications. And when the proportion of the country's population entering some form of postsecondary education approaches 50 (and in some sectors of the society, it is then of course much higher), attendance in higher education becomes increasingly seen as an obligation: for children from the middle and upper middle classes – in European countries as well as in the United States – failure to go on to higher education from secondary school is increasingly considered a mark of some defect of mind or character that has to be explained, justified, or apologized for. (Trow, 2005, p. 17)

It should be noted that the Europe 2020 strategy, adopted in 2010, sets up the following measurable target:

EU target already met by non-EU countries

A target on educational attainment ... increasing the share of the population aged 30–34 having completed tertiary education from 31% to at least 40% in 2020. (European Commission, 2010)

This quantitative benchmark is set up in order to reach the value of this indicator at the level of USA. Remarkably, this declared EU target would be already met in all four NIS countries at issue by the Millennium 2000, or even earlier.

It is on this background that a qualitative issue needs to be addressed, which could be presented in a quasi-rhetorical question, 'Is this intensive growth of higher education in EHEA countries an entirely positive development, or are there negative sides of the process as well?'

The above statistics, as well as policy considerations, only and exclusively describe the quantitative parameters of the growth of higher education in the region at issue. If one starts looking deeper into qualitative characteristics of modern national HE systems, one can make some surprising discoveries about the less desired outcomes of the process. For instance, in the case of Russia, an absolute European, if not the world-wide leader in the quantitative growth of HE both in terms of the cumulative attainment and the ongoing enrolment, there are numerous calls and warnings regarding the lowering quality of HE as the price society pays for this unprecedented growth (cf. Smetanina, 2012; Chirikov, 2015; Grove, 2015; Chvorostov, 2016). As a result, the HE authorities of the Russian government are determined to set up

Quality vs quantity of HE

targets aimed at drastic reductions of low-quality providers in the sector (cf. Semyonov; 2015; NEWSru.com, 2016).

Focus on positivist description of E:V survey outcomes

While stating this, the article will focus on the positivist, in a way as Auguste Comte suggests, description of E:V survey outcomes. The descriptive character of this article means that its primary aim is to present the yielded fresh empirical (sociological and statistical) data instead of going immediately into an in-depth exploratory analysis of the presented phenomenology. In many instances, a good and systematic presentation of data, in comparative perspective, illuminates possible routes for a subsequent and more thorough look into these data. Thus, in the most cases we would leave aside value judgements, having set as a target a compact presentation of survey outcomes.

4. Becoming a Student, the Demographics and Social Background of the Student Population

4.1 Familial Roots – Educational Attainment of Parents, their Social Standing and Migration Background

Decision for higher education within family

In most cases, the decision to opt for higher education is made within a family, or at least in accordance with the attitude of the family toward its children (would-be-students). This can be an easy and natural decision in the case of a forthcoming student who would just be continuing a generation-old tradition of a family. However, in some cases becoming a student could be a challenging move, because it may stand for a break of the familial ‘path’ and because it often entails significant expenses, such as tuition fees, the related living and accommodation costs, etc. and the delayed entrance to the labour market. Thus, a family and its views and habits often have a decisive word to say with regard to decisions on entering higher education.

4.1.1 Educational attainment of parents

The statistics used in the previous section were borrowed from the UNESCO sources, i.e. UIS, the UNESCO Institute for Statistics. They perfectly support the E:V survey’s data, which show that there is a high rate of contemporary students’ parents who have completed tertiary education themselves. In a sense, the HE is a socially inherited feature of the well-educated strata. But this state of art describes only one half of HE students, as shown in Figure 4. Another half of students come from families without a HE background.

Nowadays (on E:V average) every second HE student in EHEA stems from the families with background in higher education. The highest rates of educational inheritance demonstrate students from NIS and Northern clusters and the lowest rates, students from the Southern geographical cluster.

Every second student from families with HE background

Figure 4 All HE students whose parents have obtained tertiary education, in % (D2)⁵

However, as regards this parameter, variation is quite sizeable. Thus, in Malta and Italy (Southern cluster) only 28%⁶ of students are descendants of parents with higher education. In these countries the cumulative HE attainment is relatively low as well and is measured at 16% (MT) and 13% (IT) as compared to normally high levels of HE enrolment achieved in the current decade. Such situation is caused by the very rapid increase in HE participation in these countries, where the growth over the last 50 years was very intense, from 7% of HE participation in the 1970s to 44% in the 2010s in Malta and 23% to 65% for the same period in Italy.

Lowest rate of educational inheritance: Malta and Italy

On another pole, we found two countries with the highest rate of educational inheritance, fixed at 73%–74%. These countries are Armenia and Georgia (both are parts of the NIS region). UIS statistics demonstrate the rates of cumulative HE attainment in the upper segment of EHEA, 44% in Armenia and 31% in Georgia respectively. As regards the GER, this indicator shows the dynamics from 19% in 1980s to 48% in 2010s for Armenia (rapid growth) and 30% to 33% in Georgia (moderate growth, though from the higher base).

Highest rate of educational inheritance: Armenia and Georgia

⁵ Here and hereafter, the alphanumeric code in brackets stands for a reference to the respective section (topic) of the project's online database <http://database.eurostudent.eu/>.

⁶ Here and hereafter, the quoted data and percentages are calculated from the E:V data base if another source is not explicitly mentioned.

4.1.2 Higher education and social status

Majority of HE students from middle socio-economic strata

Furthermore, if one looks at the distribution of the self-assessed social standing of student families (Figure 5), a first and obvious observation would be that in all geographical regions the middle-level strata comprises 54% to 59% of the whole population. The main discrepancies relate to the shares of lower and upper strata.

As to the individual countries in the E:V sample, the self-attribution of the respondents to the upper strata (range 1 to 3 on the ten-point scale) is highest among the students’ families from Norway and Austria (54% and 41% respectively, against 25% of E:V average). On the other pole, the lowest perceived social standing (points 7–10 on ten-point scale) can be found among HE students from Ukraine and Romania with scores of 34% and 32% respectively (cf. 17% on E:V average).

Figure 5 Social standing of students’ parents (subjective assessment, 10-point-scale) (D7)

In all these most ‘prosperous’ and ‘deprived’ cases, the shown values of the indicator are almost two times higher than E:V averages and the averages for the respective sub-regions (geographical clusters).

4.1.3 Familial roots: Migration background

Almost every fifth HE student has a migration background

Obtaining HE is often linked with geographical mobility, a significant part of which is constituted by cross-border migration moves. As Figure 6 shows, almost every fifth HE student in E:V sample would have migration background, either being a first or second generation migrant coming from a country different to the place of study. Besides, one should account the rate of inbound student mobility⁷ that embrac-

⁷ UIS definition of Inbound Internationally Mobile Students: “Students who have crossed a national or territorial border for the purpose of education and

es for 2% to 8% of national student populations in Europe that would fall, in terms of E:V, under the category ‘first generation migrants’, but constitute only a part of respondents of this type.

Figure 6 Migrant students (according to own and parents’ country of birth), in % (A15) and inbound student mobility rates (UIS, average for 2010–2014), in %

As is visible from the chart, the average value for the share of migrant students in E:V sample is 18%, with equal parts standing for the first and second generation migrants. Regionally, the most attractive geographical cluster turned to be the Northern one (21%), while the NIS region concludes the list with 15% share of migrant students.

A country-level analysis reveals three absolute champions of E:V supra-region with regard to the shares of students with migration background. These leaders are Switzerland (44% of such students in total, of which 21% are the migrants themselves and 23% stem from migrated families). The second place holds Denmark (32% students of migrations background, of which 26% are the first-generation academic ‘pilgrims’ and only 6% are from migrant families). The third country in the list is Sweden (33% in total, 22% from the 1st generation and 11% from the 2nd generation of migrants).

Most students with migration background in Switzerland and Denmark

The outsiders with regard to this parameter are Georgia (1.5% of student population would have any migrant background), Poland and Romania (for both countries – only 2% of such students).

Few students with migration background

are now enrolled outside their country of origin.” (<http://data.uis.unesco.org/index.aspx?queryid=169#>)

A further remark is borrowed from the Synopsis of the EURO-STUDENT's survey:

Students with migration background: In two thirds of the EURO-STUDENT countries, the share of 2nd generation migrants does not exceed 10%. Switzerland, Montenegro, Germany, Estonia, Croatia, and Ukraine, with shares above 15%, are the six EURO-STUDENT countries with the highest share of 2nd generation migrant students. (Hauschildt, 2015, p. 59)

4.2 EUROSTUDENT Survey: Timing of the Transition in to Higher Education, Age and Dependents of Students

The evolution of the system of higher education from an elitist to a mass-institution and, in a final turn, into a universal system implies considerable changes in the composition of the student body. Nowadays, the studentship includes younger and older students, those with and without prior working or studying experiences, also more female students and a higher proportion of students with their own families and children. This is a new social reality of the higher education. It deserves a closer look at multi-faceted socio-demographic features of the contemporary HE contingent in the E:V sample of EHEA countries.

4.2.1 Transition into higher education: Timing

Approach of the survey

Widening access to higher education implies, among other effects, the diversification of routes to becoming a HE student. The E:V survey included a comprehensive set of questions revealing possible modalities for admission to HE. Due to quite high variance in national policies with regard to the recruitment of HE students, this sub-chapter shall only discuss the 'roof-indicator', i.e. the time lag between obtaining a complete upper secondary education degree (ISCED-3) and enrolment into a HE establishment.

Early age students in the Southern region

The first and immediate observation from the related figure (Figure 7) is that early age students are mostly found in the Southern geographical region, where the average distance in time between leaving the school and start of HE study is only 8 months. Indeed, the champions in the league turned out to be French (0 months), Croatian (1 month), and Maltese students (3 months).

Average delay in Northern countries more than two years

Students from the Northern cluster mark the opposite pole, with an average delay of more than two years (25 months), and with the leaders in the category being Finland (36 months), Norway (39 months) and Sweden (42 months).

Generally, transition from high school to a university takes some time: an average time-gap between leaving the school classroom and entering a university lecture hall is measured for E:V at an average of 15 months and the regional variation is quite considerable.

Figure 7 Average delay in months between the completion of secondary education and entering a HE programme, in months

4.2.2 Students' age

Age of HE students is a parameter closely connected with the timing of transition from secondary to higher education as well as the total duration of HE study. As the summarising chart shows (Figure 8), the youngest cohort of HE students is to be found in the NIS cluster with a mean age of 21 years. The oldest student community is – not surprisingly – in the Northern region, with the mean age of students there being 26 years.

Youngest students in NIS cluster, oldest in the Northern region

Figure 8 Age profile of students in E:V samples (Mean age, years) (A1)

At country-level, the lowest mean age of students is observed in Ukraine (20 years) and Armenia, Georgia and Russia (21 years in each country). The highest mean age is among Swedish and Norwegian students (29 years), as well as in Ireland (27 years).

4.2.3 Students and their children

Highest proportion in Norway, lowest in Ukraine

An immediate and natural consequence of an ‘advanced’ age of certain student cohorts would be that they are often emancipated from their parents’ homes and would have families of their own. The share of students having their own children (dependents) is highest in the Northern region (16%), which is two times above the E:V average (see Figure 9). The highest proportion of students with children is in Norway (25%), Sweden (21%) and Estonia (20%) and the lowest scores demonstrate students from Bosnia and Herzegovina (3%), Georgia (2%) and Ukraine (1%).

Figure 9 Share of students with children among all students, in % (A7)

5. Interim Conclusions and Practical Implications

Mass higher education in the first half of the 20th century

Using the conceptual language and frameworks of Martin Trow’s model of the quantitative evolution of HE systems, it can be stated that the transition from ‘elitist’ to ‘mass’ higher education in Europe took place during the first half of 20th century, and that the leap from the mass to a universal system occurred in the European Higher Education Area mostly in 1990s–2000s (see Figure 1). During these two decades the gross enrolment rates in HE have reached and mostly exceeded the Trow’s symbolic benchmark of 50%, when more than one half of the youth cohort (17 to 34 years old) is opting for HE. In the current decade, the 2010s, there are only a few countries left where the GER is below this threshold in the E:V sample; these are Bosnia and Herzegovina, Malta, Georgia and Armenia, while the remaining 25 countries play in the higher league.

Next benchmark of the rate of HE enrolment: 75%?

In order to better mark up the new social reality in higher education, it would be perhaps worthwhile to introduce a next benchmark at the level of, say 75% of HE participation (enrolment), which could be conventionally labelled as the status of ‘post-modern HE’, or to con-

tinue the logical sequence of Trow's quantitative labels, the elitist, mass and universal higher education is followed by a stage of total spread of higher education. In the sample of 29 E:V countries, by 2014 there will be six cases falling under this category: Russia (77%), Denmark (78%), Lithuania (79%), Slovenia (86%), Ukraine (82%) and Finland (94%), with several countries being very close to this criterion (see Figure 3 showing the average values for the period 2000–2014).

Evaluating the practical implications of such rapid growth of HE, one should take an account of a number of contextual societal factors. One of these could be the related quality parameters of national HE systems, which is dropping in some cases of 'advanced enrolment', as is evident for Russia and, most probably, would be the case in several other countries. Another societal macro-factor that should be borne in mind relates to the structural dynamics of labour markets in terms of assessment of their ability to absorb the ever-growing share of HE graduates⁸.

Growth of HE should be compared with societal factors and related to the quality parameters

Further empirical observations that can be derived from the available E:V data and which have been shortly discussed in this article would lead to several other qualitative findings. First, the HE population is getting more and more heterogeneous. Today it reflects the social structure of the society at large to a greater extent. Approximately one half of the total student body stems from families with higher education background, but, remarkably, another half stands for the pure extension of the social base of HE (see Figure 4). Furthermore, the structure of students' social standing reflects by and large the spread of socio-economic well-being in a society (Figure 5). Moreover, the share of students with migration background also becomes statistically visible (Figure 6).

HE population in EHEA is getting more heterogeneous

Secondly, there are considerable variations among E:V regions and individual countries regarding the age of students, the amount of time between secondary education graduation and entrance into higher education institutions, and the share of students with children. In all these interrelated instances, a trend can be detected that the student population in the Northern countries is older as compared to their Southern peers and fellow-colleagues from the NIS region.

Variations among E:V regions

The age factor of HE students can be regarded as an ambivalent feature. There are many advantages of being a young student. For instance, a positive facet of that is the personal time invested in professional education. A less wanted aspect is the lesser social experience

⁸ The latter issue is discussed in the forthcoming articles by the author: "HE Graduates and Qualified Jobs in EHEA: Regional Labour Market Equilibriums Under Conditions of Massification and Universalisation of Higher Education".

of studentship that may cause the even less degree of rationality behind the decision to pursue the HE studies as such and to choose a particular field of specialisation.

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Biography:

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